

A NARRATIVE INQUIRY OF SPECIAL NEEDS TEACHERS IN EDUCATING LEARNERS WITH SPECIAL EDUCATIONAL NEEDS AND DISABILITIES

Chibert L. Jala, DM, PhD

Graduate Study, Saint Columban College, Pagadian City, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16095810>

ABSTRACT

SNED teachers face complex challenges in educating learners with disabilities, requiring careful consideration of diverse factors affecting both student learning and teacher well-being. This study explored public school elementary and secondary SNED teachers' experiences educating LSEND in Cagayan de Oro City (SY 2024-2025). This qualitative study employed Polkinghorne's narrative inquiry that explored six public school SNED teachers with 10 years and above experience in the profession. Data were collected ethically through semi-structured one-on-one interviews. Findings revealed that SNED teachers' motivations by nurturing the passion for LSENDs, resonating with the family of LSEND, giving into family influence, having a desire to provide for family needs, and capitalizing on career opportunities. Its rewarding element steamed from emotional support, continuous innovative teaching strategies, a wider scope of collaboration, and adaptability and resilience. The challenges come from mental-physical fatigue and the complexity of IEP design. Then, navigating it through practicing self-care, mustering the courage to ask for help, establishing stronger partnerships with stakeholders, and implementing practical interventions. Teachers' aspirations are more authentic inclusive practices for LSEND education, stronger advocacy of independent learning for the LSENDs, and placement of more trained and proficient SNED teachers. It was concluded that experienced SNED teachers, driven by personal and professional motivations, find fulfillment in supporting learners despite challenges and remain committed to promoting inclusion, independence, and improved placement and teacher training. It was recommended that all stakeholders be encouraged to collaboratively strengthen special needs education (SNED), address teacher challenges, enhance training and resources, promote inclusion, and support continued research and advocacy

Keywords: *SNED teachers motivation, SNED teachers challenges and SNED teachers Aspiration*

INTRODUCTION

The journey of Special Needs Education (SNED) teachers has proven to be varied and filled with unique challenges. Educating students with special needs requires a demanding, multifaceted approach beyond traditional pedagogy or the regular curriculum. These navigate the complex educational landscape that carefully considers each student's diverse learning needs, emotional well-being, and physical capabilities. They continuously develop and enhance the curricula through IEP, which fosters LSEND individual growth. This requires deep pedagogical expertise, patience, empathy, and a strong commitment to individualized learning. This career overall makes it the most demanding yet profoundly rewarding educational role. This journey of SNED teachers includes the collaborative process with parents, therapists, and other professionals to develop comprehensive support plans addressing every student's development aspect.

Dumilig and Abdulrahman (2024) noted that the educational environment for learners with special educational needs and disabilities (LSENDs) has become increasingly complex. Teaching these students requires SNED teachers to show strong dedication, resilience, and a deep understanding of diverse learning challenges. However, they often face obstacles such as limited resources, outdated school facilities, and social stigma about disabilities. To effectively support their students, SNED teachers must remain committed, adaptable, creative, and emotionally strong.

The SNED teaching profession is both reflection and transformative. Teachers grow and evolve with the changing educational landscape, driven by personal and professional development.

In response to these challenges, the Department of Education issued DepEd Order No. 44, s. 2021, which aims to foster inclusive education by addressing cultural, legal, and systemic barriers in order to promote equitable access to quality education by improving curriculum design and strengthening support for LSEND learners in mainstream classrooms.

Inclusive education policies are essential for supporting students' academic, emotional, and social development. However, implementing these policies requires significant changes in teaching practices and school environments. Individualized instruction poses a big challenge especially in the Philippine context, where many teachers assigned to SNED programs are not graduates of special education programs. This lack of formal preparation contributes to high turnover rates and burnout, ultimately affecting the quality of education provided to students with disabilities. Understanding and supporting these LSEND students with disabilities requires a comprehensive approach that includes emotional, social, and instructional considerations.

Special Needs Education teachers who has the important role in creating inclusive learning environments for students with special educational needs and disabilities. They work closely with specialists and other colleagues to foster positive and productive settings. Yet, facing significant challenges, including providing academic support, promoting social inclusion, and managing the demanding nature of their jobs.

These challenges that draw teachers for continuous improvement align with the principles of the Kaizen philosophy that provides a reflective approach and enables SNED teachers to grow, remain motivated, and stay committed to enhancing learning environments. By encouraging self-driven progress, it helps teachers find purpose and opportunities for development, even in the face of difficulties. By learning from challenging experiences, they can transform setbacks into chances for personal and professional growth.

This discussion underscores more inclusive teaching practices, stronger support systems for educators, and greater cultural acceptance of learners with disabilities. It emphasizes the importance of reflection, continuous professional development, and resilience in overcoming the challenges faced by SNED teachers. At the same time, it highlights the value of holistic and inclusive strategies to effectively support both LSEND learners and the teachers who educate them.

Current research has a significant gap, as most studies focus related to SPED are mostly on teaching strategies and inclusive education policies while overlooking the personal motivations and challenges faced by Special Needs Education (SNED) teachers, especially in the context of Learners with Special Educational Needs and Disabilities (LSENDs).

This study investigates the lived experiences of Special Needs Education (SNED) teachers in educating learners with special educational needs and disabilities (LSENDs). It examines their motivations, challenges, and aspirations for professional growth, aiming to demonstrate how their efforts contribute to positive outcomes for LSEND learners. To bridge the existing research gap, this study emphasizes the emotional and psychological dimensions of their work areas often overlooked in current literature. By understanding the unique perspectives and inner experiences of SNED teachers, the research seeks to strengthen teacher support systems, guide relevant professional development, and ultimately enhance the learning experiences of LSEND students.

Research Questions

The study explores the lived experiences of Special Needs Education (SNED) teachers in educating learners with special educational needs and disabilities (LSENDs) in public elementary and secondary schools in Cagayan de Oro City for the school year 2024–2025. The study focused on answering the central question: How do SNED teachers experience educating LSENDs?

Specifically, the study specifically answered the following sub-questions:

1. What motivates SNED teachers to pursue a career in Special Needs Education?
2. What are the rewarding aspects of educating LSEND students?
3. What challenges do SNED teachers face when educating LSEND students?
4. How do SNED teachers navigate the challenges involved in educating LSEND students?
5. What are the aspirations of the SNED teachers for their LSEND students?

METHODOLOGY

The research employed a qualitative narrative inquiry design to explore the lived experiences of Special Needs Education (SNED) teachers educating learners with special educational needs and disabilities (LSENDs) in public elementary and secondary schools in Cagayan de Oro City during the 2024–2025 school year. This approach allowed for in-depth exploration of teachers' motivations, challenges, aspirations, and coping strategies through their personal narrative stories. Selected six teachers from elementary and secondary SNED public schools with at least ten years of experience were purposefully chosen as participants to ensure contextually grounded insights. Data collection was conducted through semi-structured interviews using an interview guide, with the researcher serving as the primary instrument. Ethical protocols such as informed consent, confidentiality, and adherence to the Data Privacy Act of 2012 were strictly followed throughout the study.

The data were analyzed using Polkinghorne's (1995) narrative and thematic analysis approach, involving the systematic stages of organizing, coding, identifying themes, and interpreting meanings. Audiorecorded interviews were transcribed, anonymized, and securely stored. Through repeated readings and coding of narratives, recurring themes and insights related to SNED teachers' experiences were identified and contextualized. This analysis provided a deeper understanding of the emotional, psychological, and professional aspects of teaching LSENDs. The methodology ensured that the voices of SNED teachers were authentically represented, offering valuable contributions to special education research and practical implications for policy, teacher support, and inclusive education practices

RESULTS

The study showed the results on teachers' motivations pursuing the career in Special Needs Education, the rewarding aspects of the job, the challenges they face, and the aspiration to the LSEND. The six teachers with over 10 years of experience, were purposely selected and identified by code names: Teachers Abby, Baze, Cath, Dayl, Enn, and Fay. The narrative about their insights and personal stories based on their lived experiences.

Teacher Abby: The Diligent

Teacher Abby, a SNED teacher at Central Elementary School for thirteen years, holds a Bachelor of Elementary Education (Early Childhood Development) and is pursuing a Master's in SPED. Her experience as a mother of a child with Asperger's Syndrome informs her compassionate and effective teaching style, allowing her to connect with students and families and advocate for their needs. Her diligence, meticulous preparation, and clear communication highlight her professionalism and commitment to creating supportive learning environments for diverse learners.

Teacher Abby's Motivation in Pursuing the Career

Her career was deeply rooted in raising a daughter with Asperger's Syndrome. The challenges shaped her commitment to supporting children with special needs. While professional growth played a role, her main drive was ensuring other children received the individualized attention they often lacked, using her personal experiences to fuel her advocacy.

..it all started when I was raising my two children at a very young age. My daughter was diagnosed with Asperger's Syndrome when she was five.

..early years were a whirlwind of therapies, specialist appointments, and educational battles. Me going to the educational system to ensure Lily received the appropriate support was a constant uphill struggle. I learned to advocate fiercely for her, I became a master of paperwork and a negotiator with teachers and administrators.

..you know what, raising Lily taught me something that i wanted to be in my career, my husband supported me all throughout these challenges from a plain simple wife and shaping myself to pursue this career. So, I decided to be an elementary teacher specializing in the SPED program.

Teacher Abby's decision to pursue Special Education naturally stems from her journey as a mother. Inspired by her love for her children and the lessons learned to be patience, advocacy, and understanding diverse needs, she transitioned from a simple wife to a passionate teacher. Her story showed motherhood and its learning can lead to personal growth and a purposeful career dedicated to helping children with special needs.

Teacher Abby rewarding moments as SNED teacher

Teacher Abby finds the most rewarding moments in special education through her students' small but meaningful progress, gestures like a confident smile, eye contact, or initiating conversation. These deep milestones reflect growing confidence and skill, deeply fueling her passion. Inspired by these daily victories, she continually seeks new strategies and collaborates with peers, showing her strong commitment to ongoing professional growth.

..the most rewarding aspect of working with students with special needs is witnessing their growth and progress, no matter how small it is. Same with Lily's daily changes, always give me the excitement about something daily. ..I recall one student, a bright but always agitated student who struggled with social interactions. The simple act of making eye contact and initiating a conversation felt amazing. As I see it is working, slowly, patiently, using role-playing, social stories ..this is the I see it inspiring and keeping me reinforced with so many strategies believing that everyone has something valuable to develop

Teacher Abby's approach to students with disabilities who display self-inflicted behaviors involves empathy, careful observation, and proactive strategies to build self-awareness and coping skills. One meaningful moment showed when a student with social disability confidently asked her a question; this act symbolized more than academic progress. For teacher Abby, success lies in the compassion and patience poured into each child. The student's ability to overcome anxiety reaffirmed her belief in every learner's potential and deepened her commitment. Despite opportunities for higher pay elsewhere, Abby chooses to stay, finding greater reward in the purpose and fulfillment her role provides.

Teacher Abby's challenges of Educating LSENDs

Working with its experience towards students with special needs often presents challenges in understanding and managing self-harming behaviors. Teachers Abby experience on the challenging action, frequently stemming from unmet needs or difficulties in communication, require teachers to develop immense patience, empathy, and flexible strategies to help students find healthier ways to express themselves.

..I remember one of the most frequent difficulties when educating SPED student is the behaviors, particularly those involving of self-inflicted harm while hearing stories from their yaya's and parents the same sentiment that they have also those kind of questions "how do they feel"

..I also remember a student, a bright but intensely sensitive girl who frequently scratched and hit herself when she was happy. I made a discovery along the way which I tried to focus on redirecting her behavior through activities. But it became clear that this approach serves me a light that the students struggled to express her emotions, her frustration manifesting as physical self-harm.

Teacher Abby's journey reveals the emotional challenges of working with students who exhibit self-harming behaviors. She experiences moments of frustration and uncertainty but grows through empathy and understanding. Abby recognizes that self-harm often stems from unexpressed emotions, sensory overload, or communication struggles. This insight shifts her approach from simple redirection to deeper emotional support. She highlights the toll it takes on both students and herself, stressing the need for patience, flexibility, and adaptability especially since most of his students are

undiagnosed children. Her growth is shown in her willingness to reflect, to adjust, and to keep learning.

Teacher Abby is navigating through the challenges of educating LSENDs

Teacher Abby's resilience and awareness navigate the challenges driven by pride and a strong work ethic, recognizing her limits when facing overwhelming challenges. A particularly demanding week, characterized by multiple students experiencing diverse emotional and learning difficulties, pushed her to her physical and emotional limits. This experience was a turning point, causing her to re-evaluate her approach to managing stress and burnout. This characteristic showed the importance of self-care and seeking colleague support, showing her emotional intelligence and commitment to sustainable well-being, ultimately strengthening her teaching practice.

..I remember one particularly challenging week with my student who at the same time was experiencing emotional responses through tantrums, another was struggling with sensory overload, and a third was having difficulty processing information. Surely this student required a different approach, add adding up the different story of my daughter

..I found myself working very exhausted up until night, reflecting and prepping materials for tomorrow, and trying to review these potential challenges. The exhaustion was very noticeable, a heavy weight settling on my shoulders.

.. during that week I realized the importance of self-care and seeking support from my colleagues. I had always my pride, on my resilience and ability to handle pressure, but I had reached a point that pushing through was no longer sustainable.

Teacher Abby's effective teaching relies on collaboration with colleagues and family. Facing challenges educating LSEND students, she initially relied on resilience and a strong work ethic, but realized it wasn't a long-term solution. She even shifted to prioritize self-care (exercise, meditation, conversations with her husband), and built a supportive core group with colleagues through shared experiences and discussions. This helped her reset and better support her students.

Teacher Abby's Aspiration for the LSEND

The aspirations are deeply rooted in her understanding of the complexities of special education. Inspired by her daughter's journey, she is committed to becoming a proficient SNED teacher, viewing challenges as opportunities for empowerment. The goal is to help children with disabilities unlock their full potential, creating progress and fostering their independence to thrive in the community. Teacher Abby's approach reflects her dedication to nurturing the unique strengths of each child. Fueled by her passion and personal experiences, she aims to inspire others and contribute to a more inclusive society. Her aspiration is not merely to excel professionally but to make a tangible difference in the lives of her students, helping them reach their exemplary potential in the

direction of fostering independence and functional skills and enabling her students to participate more fully in their communities.

...if you think this is the professional job that you will be able to excel professionally nah! you might end up frustrated specially that opportunities might be a good option. This is not a simple job but to zeal of character of every individual like me, reflecting and looking at my daughter without me ..my aspiration to be a proficient SPED teacher even though this isn't simple to teach children with disabilities. The process itself empower me to help this kids reach their full potential

Teacher Abby's aspiration to her students as an SNED teacher stems from a deep personal connection whose experience has the same story as hers. This kind of commitment to empowering students, recognizing their unique potential, and understanding diverse learning styles reflects a characteristic of passion and dedication. Unlike those seeking purely professional advancement, Abby's unwavering commitment to making a lasting impact on children with disabilities drives her work, transforming her professional goal into a deeply meaningful aspiration.

Teacher Baze: The Steward

Teacher Baze has eleven years of experience in a large secondary public school and is pursuing a Master's degree in SPED, demonstrating her commitment to professional growth. Her permanent position as a SPED Teacher 1 and her Bachelor of Secondary Education provides an opportunity for a strong foundation for working with adolescents. She manages the LSEND program, making her well-equipped to support secondary students with disabilities. Her personal journey, marked by family hardship and her brother's social challenges, fueled her passion for education and developed her empathy for marginalized children. This experience and her commitment to continuous improvement allow her to create a compassionate learning environment for students with special needs.

Teacher Baze's Motivation in Pursuing the Career

In pursuing a career in special education as a teacher, Baze marked the experiences that scarred the challenges faced by her family, particularly her brother, who struggled with social engagement. The social challenge, social acceptance, and the limited resources in their town fueled her sense of injustice and determination to make a difference. Her proactive efforts to teach her brother to read highlighted her commitment to addressing the gaps in support for children with disabilities. This hands-on experience improved not only herself but also gave character to her academic excellence in the growing demand for special education programs. Ultimately, Teacher Baze's journey is a powerful blend of being a steward in the family and its desire for social advocacy and awareness of LSEND's abilities.

..as a breadwinner , my journey wasn't just about teaching, it was filled with different aspiration in life, a way to alleviate some of the hardship of my family that had endured

..this personal experience was transformed from my own personal story in which I had a brother who had a problem in social engagement. He didn't play with other kids, he didn't make eye contact, he didn't understand what's happening around. Since we live in the small town, issues like our brother is either cursed or determined that it has mental problem

..I poured myself into my studies, focusing on education and child development, then took up a teaching degree with a specialization in special education.

Teacher Baze's motivation to teach special education is a blend of selfless concern for her students and a desire to improve her family's economic situation. Her academic success and career choice were partly driven by a need to escape poverty, and the advice she received about career opportunities in special education solidified her decision. Her personal experiences drive its dedication to fostering resilience and understanding of the challenges her students face.

Teacher Baze's rewarding elements for Educating LSEND

The dedication to LSEND students is a personal mission of teacher Baze, which is fueled by empathy and the joy of their growth. A student calling her "Teacher Baze," echoing its excitement, showed the emotional rewards she experiences. This seemingly small act holds immense significance for her, representing the fruitful presence of learning and communication address and the built personal connection she fosters with her students. Despite limited resources in the department, she creatively adapts her teaching to support students with memory and mental health challenges. The fact that her students remember her name highlights her commitment and the transformative impact of her work on their lives. This story illustrates the challenges and fulfillment of teaching LSEND students and the joy of witnessing their self-discovery.

..when I remember one of my student call me by my name "Teacher Baze," a soft voice whispered, was shocked and amazed, not on the gesture but it was like someone call me as family

..my role as a teacher wasn't simply to teach, it was also their hope and joy on their challenging journey. As I reflect in their learning journey and self-discovery

..public school resources is not enough, we innovate, materials are scarce and divert to playfull strategy that drained much of energy

The most rewarding aspect of teaching special education for Teacher Baze is the profound connection she builds with her students. The warmth and trust reflected in them calling her "Teacher Baze" highlight her essential role in their growth. Knowing her work positively impacts not only her students but their families as well, coupled with the personal satisfaction of witnessing their progress, makes her role as a breadwinner deeply fulfilling.

Teacher Baze's navigating through the challenges of educating LSENDs

The numerous challenges and barriers faced by teacher Baze as a teacher in LSEND, which give most of the significant obstacles, are inadequate access to assistive technology and other necessary materials, which is a constant struggle in her classroom, especially in the growing community of LSEND learners with multiple disabilities. The recounts a distressing experience with a student diagnosed specifically with cerebral palsy that consumes a lot of time in communicative discovery, sometimes falling into accidentally harmed LSEND student where it triggers its action to connect. Sometimes, the lack of funding and resources can feel like a daunting battle, forcing teachers to rely solely on their skills and creativity to meet their students' needs.

...of course! inadequate access to assistive technology and other material is our constant battle

..caters multiple disabilities in one classroom setting with mostly the same number of student in the normal classroom

Teacher Baze faces significant challenges educating special needs students in a limited resource and poor environment. The delays in procuring essential assistive technology and materials leave her struggling to meet the student's needs, as highlighted by a case involving a student with cerebral palsy. This lack of resources, coupled with her family responsibilities, adds to her workload and frustration. Despite these difficulties, she demonstrates remarkable adaptability and resilience.

Teacher Baze Navigating the Challenges in Parental resistance

Parents with the most significant factors affecting individual learning are observed in the teacher's experience as she navigates this challenge into the support provided by schools. Educators need to engage with parents' empathy and establish collaborative partnerships. Their crucial role in reinforcing learning and managing behavior at home may support the condition that their child's special learning needs be supported. By fostering open communication and involving parents in decision-making, teachers are more likely to promote a positive environment that supports the academic success and emotional well-being of students with special needs.

..telling the parents that their child needs extra specific support but does not response either they are in denial stage or leave everything to the school

..giving technical support and communication that seek support from parents at home for continuous learning

Teacher Baze's experiences talking to parents about their child's need for extra support show a different emotional reaction. Some parents respond positively, while others deny the need for help. Teachers strive to have clear and accessible conversations, but many families from low-income backgrounds struggle to discuss available resources, leading to feelings of unsupported collaboration. Despite these challenges, she emphasizes the importance of continuous support at home. They suggest practical activities parents can do with their children to help them manage classroom

requirements. This highlights the emotional complexity of these conversations and shows Teacher Baze's commitment to creating a supportive environment for students and their families.

Teacher Baze's Aspiration for LSENDs

The individual's deep empathy and passion for SNED teachers aspire beyond the classroom, shaped by years of dedicated service with the joy of witnessing students with SNED communicate more effectively and gain confidence, which fuels her commitment to their growth. Simple acts, like helping her parents, enhance her overall fulfillment, illustrating the interconnectedness of her personal and professional life. This holistic view shows that her success with SEN learners inspires her dedication to her family and vice versa. Her pride in her work motivates her to strive for greater effectiveness in supporting her students, highlighting her aspiration to empower them on their learning journeys.

..aside from becoming my passion because of the long service in the SPED program, it is in the amazing moments seeing your students able to communicate better, gain confidence, and develop learning skills which surprise you sometimes. In your off guarded moments, deep within you are able to smile confidently saying that this is the effort that I have made through.

Teacher Baze's aspirations arise from her extensive experience in public school and spark her passion for teaching learners of special educational needs and disabilities (LSEND). She believes her role creates transformative moments when students can communicate effectively, leading to improved learning outcomes and personal pride in her work.

Her dedication extends beyond the classroom to include responsibilities towards families, motivating her to make a meaningful difference in both areas. By empowering students with special needs to communicate, Teacher Baze directly influences their progress and ability to achieve their goals, ultimately enhancing their quality of life.

Teacher Cath: The Purpose-Driven

Teacher Cath is a dedicated special needs educator with twelve years of experience at a central public elementary school. She is currently completing her Master's degree in Special Needs Education (SNED), demonstrating her commitment to excellence in supporting diverse learners. As a permanent SPED Teacher 1, she shows long-term dedication to her school. Her bachelor's degree in early childhood education equips her with a strong understanding of young children's developmental needs, which shapes her teaching methods. Additionally, her management of the inclusive LSEN program highlights her ability to create a supportive learning environment for all students. Her family life as a married woman further enhances her resilience and effectiveness.

Teacher Cath's purpose is driven from the perspective that is shaped by her personal and professional experiences. Her early inclination to help others laid the foundation for her teaching career. When two of her children were diagnosed with special needs, it deepened her commitment and intertwined her roles as a mother and teacher. This experience fostered empathy and resilience, influencing her compassionate teaching approach. She adapts her strategies to meet diverse student needs, leveraging her parenting successes. Teacher Cath's journey illustrates how personal experiences can enhance professional dedication, enabling her to create inclusive and nurturing environments where all children can thrive.

Teacher Cath's Motivation in Pursuing the Career.

The drive to pursue the career of teacher Cath in SNED teaching comes from her strong desire to help children. Growing up as the oldest of eleven siblings, with both parents working, she naturally took on the role of caregiver and educator. Taking care of her brothers and sisters, creating fun learning activities, and balancing teaching with discipline sparked her love for teaching that went beyond just childhood dreams. These experiences helped generate empathy and a deep appreciation of children's difficulties, guiding her to follow a career that allowed her to support and encourage children to reach their potential and overcome challenges.

..as the eldest, I became the teacher and the caretaker of my younger siblings. I remember during our time also the disciplinarian, the teachers, the caretaker in my early years. It was filled with very momentous challenges and rewards of teaching my siblings, for me triggers the sparks in teaching.

..along its challenging way of my life I decided I wanted to work with children, to nurture their potential, and to help them overcome challenges.

Teacher Cath's career transformed from the impact of personal experiences and intrinsic motivation. As the eldest of eleven in a working-class family, she became a teacher and caregiver for her siblings, giving them direct instruction towards basic literacy. This early exposure fostered her empathy and desire to support children facing challenges in traditional education.

Her journey took a significant turn when two of her own children were diagnosed with special needs. This diagnosis deepened her commitment to a purpose-driven life that aligns her personal and professional goals. This experience enriched her dedication, inspiring her to create a classroom environment that reflects her family's journey.

Driven by a strong commitment, this motivation lifts and empowers her students, transforming her challenges into growth opportunities. She adapts her teaching strategies to cultivate resilience and a love for learning. Her inspiring story highlights how personal experiences can catalyze one's dreams, leading to a fulfilling career focused on unlocking the unique potential of each child and nurturing their growth.

Teacher Cath's rewarding elements in Educating LSEND.

The thrive of dedication and innovative teaching methods is evident in teacher Cath's story despite the challenges in creating a supportive classroom environment. Drawing on childhood memories of engaging her siblings with educational activities, she develops hands-on, sensory-rich lessons that spark her students' interests and encourage participation. She connects with them personally by allowing them to touch, play, and explore, embodying her role as their advocate. Their resilience in turning frustrations into creative solutions promotes simple expressions of gratitude that reaffirm their purpose and fuel their passion for making a meaningful impact.

*..everytime I felt had times I traced and look back on the stories i have, to my SNED fulfilled when our memories serves as their learning
..felt the students who are appreciative that I'm sure I've created meaningful learning experiences for them like my own children*

Teacher Cath's extensive experience allows her to adapt teaching methods to each student's unique needs, adjusting the learning process in real time. She creates engaging, multi-sensory activities tailored to individual learning styles. Student expressions of gratitude, like "thank you for the experience," are deeply rewarding, validating her efforts and highlighting her profound impact. Her rewards extend beyond academic progress to include the emotional connections she builds and the positive learning experiences she creates, even amidst significant challenges. Transforming difficult situations into opportunities for growth for both herself and her students is a key aspect of her rewarding career.

Teacher Cath's challenges in Educating LSENDs

Teacher Cath faces significant challenges in managing multiple students with multi-sensory needs who are prone to self-harm, leading to exhaustion and emotional strain that shows the urgent need for better support systems and resources. She recalls a challenging incident where a student's escalating self-harm, marked by uncontrolled actions and visible injuries, deeply affected her and emphasized the overwhelming task of addressing diverse needs in a resource-limited environment. The lack of appropriate facilities, such as an isolation room or dedicated support staff, compounded the difficulties. In response, teacher Cath prioritized the student's immediate needs, seeking comfort and understanding the reasons behind the outburst. She also contacted the parents and underscored the challenges she faces in her role.

*...in the classroom with more than 20 students with different multiple and diverse needs felt very heavy while recognizing differences from a self-harming behavior and other differences
..I don't have an isolation area or any specific facilities to de-escalate the situation, I contacted her parents, but they were also working. I exerted*

extra effort to understand her, and eventually, she calmed down. I felt like I had made it through that day.

..you know what drained my energy? I'm small, and my physical strength isn't enough to handle adults. The weight of responsibility was immense during that time. I was a lone soldier fighting against overwhelming odds; it wasn't a lack of choices, but a matter of managing the situation with the resources I had at the moment.

Teacher Cath showed the challenges that arise from managing classrooms filled with students with diverse and complex needs, compounded by a lack of adequate resources and support. Cath's experience illustrates the difficulty of balancing instructional goals with the immediate emotional and behavioral needs of distressed students. She feels overwhelmed by her responsibilities, exacerbated by physical limitations and insufficient support staff. This situation underscores the urgent need for changes in schools, highlighting the personal sacrifices teachers make and the importance of improved training, resources, and staffing to effectively support all students, particularly those facing serious challenges.

Teacher Cath Navigating through the challenges in Educating LSENDs

The experience of teacher Cath navigating the challenges showed the importance and value of parents and teachers working together through the demanding reality of teaching students with diverse needs are in need. Teacher Cath works through escalating emotional and physical outbursts, highlighting the immediate challenges and the subsequent reflections that lead to crucial parent-teacher conferences and parental support.

..to have parent-teacher conferences were scheduled immediately where I discussed the impulsive outcome and shared what had happened during the time of the escalated tantrums and turns into physical outbursts.

...discussion to the parents that the lack of parental involvement could create immense pressure, ask them also for the solutions if they wanted to attain the objective we wanted to.

..there should be collaboration

Teacher Cath's parent-teacher conference strategy with SNED students involves collaborative problem-solving, emphasizing the importance of parental involvement in managing challenging behaviors. In her strategy, she recognizes that parental participation varies, with some parents actively seeking support. This collaborative approach, combined with her resourcefulness and dedication, allows her to navigate challenges effectively. She acts as a bridge, translating complex educational concepts into accessible language for parents, fostering open communication and shared responsibility in addressing complex issues related to special needs education. Valuing parental insights enhances her ability to support students effectively.

Teacher Cath's Aspiration for the LSENDs

The strength shown by teacher Cath looking into the guidelines aligns with the department's rules and objective for inclusive education, the direction of individualized learning plans tailored to each student's specific needs and abilities. The goal of the curriculum is to hope that, if properly engaged, it may cultivate every customer involved, equipping LSEND learners with the tools to navigate the world confidently and achieve their personal goals. Every child, regardless of their challenges, deserves the opportunity to reach their full potential, and it's this belief that fuels my daily work and informs my aspirations for my LSEND students.

*..my approach was always rooted to my objective about my student. Not to much on academic but through life skills
..seeing them and discovering a remarkable talent promotes my aspiration to keep on track
..it's not about the salary, we get paid, and we don't go unpaid, it's about living it every day, changing other lives every day, and also changing my own life, emotionally and physically
..I find this as a mission that I am called to serve for them and while nourishing them, while I also nourish my three kids and my family and being motivated to do it again and again.*

The story implies that this aspiration is rooted in prioritizing the life skills teaching approach to LSEND. A commitment to preparing them for real-world challenges reflects a profound understanding of their unique circumstances and the importance of fostering independence. The discovered remarkable talents in the students motivate and affirm its purpose, illustrating the emotional rewards accompanying her teaching journey. Furthermore, the connection she feels to her students, mainly when they express gratitude through their narratives, reinforces the idea that teaching is not merely a job but a calling. This reveals a holistic view of education, where nurturing students nourishes family and personal growth. This mutual transformation highlights the profound impact that SNED teachers can have on their students and their own lives as they engage in a mission that embodies a genuine commitment to service and love.

Teacher Dayl: The Caretaker

Teacher Dayl is a dedicated SNED teacher with nineteen years of experience as an SNED Teacher 1 at a central public elementary school, reflecting her long-term commitment to public service. She holds a Bachelor's degree in Elementary Education and a Master's in Special Education (SPED), underscoring her dedication to professional development. Teacher Dayl's effective management of the inclusive LSEND program and a balanced personal life enhance her effectiveness in this demanding profession.

Similarly, Teacher Cath's journey as a dedicated SPED teacher highlights her deep emotional connection to her students and her transformative joy when witnessing their growth and independence. Initially motivated by a desire to provide for her family,

Cath's focus shifted to her students' aspirations as her children became more established. This reflects her profound commitment to their success and the unique role of a special education teacher in fostering support and encouragement for students facing significant challenges. Cath's willingness to accept students even when enrollment is closed showcases her hope for recognition and her belief in their potential. Her experiences illustrate how dedicated teachers can shape positive change for learners with special educational needs.

Teacher Dayl's Motivation Pursuing Career.

The motivation to pursue a career in Special Needs Education (SNED) profoundly carried in the belief of teacher Dayl in the potential of every child's hope, regardless of their challenges. Her enduring motivation in her special education career stems from witnessing her students able to grasp the responses in the community, which means that there is increasing independence and community integration. While initially driven by familial responsibilities, her focus has shifted over time. The deep reflection of joy of seeing her students thrive and become capable of navigating their gestures with less support. This means they could adopt environmental responses, which was her primary source of motivation.

...at my age now, and after years of service as a teacher, especially in the SNED program, despite the many struggles in the beginning, it's incredibly rewarding to see my students become capable members of the community, able to go out on their own, and to know they can be independent. These are the things that bring me joy and motivate me to adapt to the changes of this time, especially since SNED requires constant upgrades and I need to constantly learn new technologies. When I was younger, my family was my motivation to continue, but now that they're established, it's my students who excite me and make me look forward to their future. If only there was a way to track where my former students are now, I would love to hear their stories.

..I pursued a graduate program in Special Education, thinking I could teach in another country. But those dreams were cut short because it was difficult to leave my children, especially since my husband worked as a driver and was often away. Those dreams faded when I saw my children excel academically. Seeing their progress, despite the burden of loans, made me focus on helping my students in the classroom. This is my way of repaying the good fortune my children have experienced.

..if you hear their stories, especially those of undiagnosed children, you'll understand that their parents are often very poor. It's a continuous cycle; their homes lack support, often only providing food. That's why, when enrollment is closing, I can't refuse requests for help. I think about their situation if they can't go to school.

The story demonstrates the action of a teacher who has navigated the challenges of working in the SPED program. Through her reflections, it becomes clear that her initial ambitions of teaching abroad were set aside for the sake of her family, particularly in light of her husband's demanding job and her responsibilities as a parent. Despite the personal sacrifices, her commitment to her students remains unwavering; she derives immense joy from witnessing their growth and capabilities within the community. She shows empathy and understanding of her students' situations by being willing to accept them even after the enrollment deadlines. This story highlights a dedicated educator's challenging yet rewarding journey, demonstrating how her love for teaching and her students' progress inspire her passion and commitment to shaping their futures despite facing her own challenges.

Teacher Dayl's rewarding elements in Educating LSEnDs

The focus on providing innovative and inclusive teaching strategies for students with diverse learning needs is shown by teacher Dayl. She believes in creating a supportive and engaging learning environment that empowers all students to reach their full potential. Her rewarding experiences stem from the successful collaboration of parents to create a supportive home environment for their children with special needs. She emphasizes the initial challenges of a lack of awareness and understanding surrounding special needs, recalling instances of children being labeled negatively. Her approach includes parents' awareness and initiative about their children's conditions and providing them with practical strategies to manage challenging behaviors at home.

..in the past, it was incredibly difficult because there wasn't much awareness about special needs children, people would call them or branded as retarded or in the mental state or problem which gives us sentiment to do something

..the participation of parents when they themselves can implement strategies at home, the collaboration with parents is key to creating a cycle of positive change for a child, ensuring that progress is made. If you can convey this to the parents, you'll see the child improve.

Teachers Dayl reveals a role that provides hope and support to students with special needs, directly giving importance to parental involvement. Past challenges stemming from a lack of parental understanding often resulted in bullying and misunderstandings. By actively engaging parents in discussions, providing practical strategies for home support, and fostering open communication, the teacher creates a collaborative environment that enhances a child's development. This collaborative approach recognizes the home environment's vital role, demonstrating that transformative change is possible through the combined efforts of educators and parents.

Teacher Dayl's challenges in Educating LSEnDs.

Teacher Dayl's challenges in Educating LSEnDs include constructing individualized education plans for each student, creating a paradigm from the content

standard at the national level, and accommodating the various activities in the department. It greatly affects the learning styles and abilities and the supportive and inclusive classroom environment. Additionally, the absence of medical diagnosis promotes a challenging enigma in the classroom environment. She describes her experience in the initial years as particularly demanding, requiring significant energy and emotional investment, often leaving her feeling depleted at the end of the day. This initial experience highlights the physical and emotional toll of managing challenging behaviors and the potential for burnout.

..teaching nature is SNED is incredibly challenging already. Education for special needs children requires fresh approaches every day, methods that are suitable for the specific children enrolled that year, because each year brings a different group. Initially, I found that managing the classroom environment and the diverse behaviors of children with different needs was exhausting. My strategies, energy, and everything I had were poured into them each day, leaving me with little time for my own growing children. I realized that each day was resolved only in the evening, after dealing with tantrums. As I've gotten older, I've realized that my initial challenges weren't the classroom strategies or the children themselves, but my own willingness to teach them. This willingness could be undermined by considering other personal options for better opportunities, consuming my attention with thoughts of alternative strategies and pursuing further courses to teach abroad. I think that's what I've seen hold other teachers back. With these children, it's not about being perfect with every strategy, but about caring for them and listening to what they need to learn; then the day will be successful. They aren't always disruptive; they listen much more often than not.

Teacher Dayl, as a SNED teacher, faces challenges but finds hope in her commitment to her students. Adaptability and fresh perspectives are crucial in meeting diverse needs. Prioritizing emotional support, attentive listening, and nurturing relationships, Her belief embodies meaningful learning that stems from connection and compassion, fostering an environment where students feel valued and understood. Her actions demonstrate that patience and understanding can help every child.

Teacher Dayl navigating through the challenges in Educating LSEnDs

Teacher Dayl explains her strategy for navigating the challenges by focusing on collaboration and seeking support from various sources. She highlights the significance of peer support and actively engages with her colleagues to share knowledge and address problems. This collaborative approach goes beyond casual conversations; she intentionally seeks their expertise and assistance, especially when working with particularly challenging students. Her openness to accepting help from colleagues reflects her humility and understanding that collective knowledge is greater than individual expertise.

...you need to remember this. Don't face challenges alone; involve your colleagues. Talk to them and listen to them, because they have hidden strengths and knowledge. This will also help them to contribute to solving your problems. My children often listen to me, but they also give me advice. We should believe that our knowledge comes from God in different ways; what isn't given to you is given to someone else, and that's where we should seek it. In my classroom, I always call on my colleagues because they're like mothers to me, and they support me. If they have a child they can't handle, they ask for my help, and I'm always willing. Nowadays, there are ways to group students according to their abilities. Before, they were all mixed together in one section, which made things much more difficult

Teacher Dayl's experience viewed the vital role of collaboration between educators, parents, and students in special needs education. This advocates for sharing challenges with colleagues, fostering a supportive environment, and recognizing the value of collective problem-solving. Viewing parents as essential partners implies a parallel dual responsibility of educating both students and families. A strong home-school connection, as exemplified by her experience with a supportive parent, significantly benefits students' learning. This collaboration enhances support for students with special needs and fosters hope for their futures, demonstrating that collective community strength is key to their success.

Teacher Dayl's Aspiration for the LSENDs.

Teacher Dayl's aspiration as a teacher in special education grows to the hope of department and societal change that will create a more inclusive and supportive environment for students with disabilities. She believes that by advocating for resources, training, and understanding, she can help shape a future where every child has the opportunity to thrive academically and socially. This optimism about the future of special education on the challenges she faced in the past highlights significant improvements in resources, classroom environments, diagnostic capabilities, parental awareness, and community openness as key indicators of progress. This positive outlook is rooted in her belief that these advancements will create greater opportunities for students with special needs to achieve their aspirations.

..I've seen the gradual improvements in the SPED program over time, something I've longed for. The resources, classrooms, student-teacher ratios, the ability to accurately diagnose (not just guess), parent awareness, training opportunities, and community openness have all improved. I'm confident that future students will have a much better chance of achieving their dreams. Before, I wasn't sure we could help them reach their ambitions. Now, with the improvements in the system and the efforts of officials, more students will be able to achieve their dreams and find fulfilling jobs. The fact that there are now government job openings is a sign that this is happening. Going forward, I will continue to care for my students as if

they were my own children, and I'll be happy to see them succeed. My dream is to have a student tell me they've gotten a government job. I have high hopes for this generation; they're capable of achieving great things.

Teacher Dayl's aspiration emerges from the future advancements in SNED through increased resources, parental involvement, training, and community support. This progress transforms her uncertainty about her students' futures into confidence in their ability to achieve their dreams. Treating her students like her own children, Dayl fosters a nurturing environment, believing that they can overcome obstacles and contribute meaningfully to society with the proper support from these advanced resources. Her high expectations, with its dedication to addressing diverse learners through active participation in their growth, embody hope for a brighter future for special needs students.

Teacher Enn: The Patriotic

Teacher Enn has served ten years as a permanent SNED Teacher 1 in a public elementary school. Her Bachelor's degree in Early Childhood Education provides a solid foundation in child development, enabling her to effectively support diverse learners. Currently pursuing a Master's degree in Special Education (SPED), she is committed to ongoing professional growth. Her role in the LSEND program showcases her ability to create an inclusive classroom environment where all students can learn and communicate. Driven by her belief in the transformative power of education, she finds motivation in witnessing her students' breakthroughs and continuously seeks to improve her teaching strategies. Her proactive engagement in professional development, willingness to face challenges, and focus on fostering a positive learning environment distinguish her as an exceptional educator. Enn prioritizes empowering her students and their families, viewing hardships as opportunities for personal and professional growth.

Teacher Enn's Motivation in Pursuing a Career.

The trust that education can transform lives and empower individuals, especially the LSENDs, illustrates the character of teacher Enn's motivation. She believes that every student can succeed by the department's vision with the proper support and guidance, and she is dedicated to providing that for her students. Her primary driving force is a belief in the transformative power of education, fueled by love and compassion for the student's cab breakthroughs and seeing their faces light up when they grasp a difficult concept. This joy isn't merely a feeling; it fuels her constant pursuit of improved teaching strategies and inspires her professional development.

..this is a deep-seated belief in the transformative power of education. There is something behind what we see as long as the presence of love and compassion to people you care for, especially to the students who really need our care. The love of seeing a student's face light up when they finally

grasp a difficult learning gives me the confidence of being a teacher. It was not simply a feeling, it is my driving force behind his constant pursuit of better teaching strategies. The will to learn in your devoured professional development excites this journey and give me more profound achievements.

..the everyday preparation and learning is very fulfilling, without thinking of the despite and other hardships you'll end up making reality of the power to change lives.

.. to transform is to live. Hardship is just in the mind, once you'll get over it you'll see yourself in the grandeur of achievement that you believe by helping these kinds of kids then you'll end up improving yourself and your career.

..enduring everything and avoiding your comfort will change your life direction. As a SNED teacher, it is necessary to keep yourself up to date with the learning trends and strategy. This is needed, since teachers want learning outcomes among our LSEND and provide them with the necessary knowledge that they can use in their daily activities. To this we will be able to contribute functional and capable students in the community. Also, a big help to their families' challenges. If we only focus on our self-care we will end up thinking of hardship and difficulties that our profession offers.

Teacher Enn inspires national pride and community contribution in her students by embodying the DepEd values as core towards development. She emphasizes continuous learning and adaptation in special education, urging teachers to prioritize student success over self-care. Enn advocates for a supportive environment where teachers' energy and expertise help students reach their full potential, fostering personal fulfillment and positive impact on students and families. Her approach highlights the connection between professional growth and student achievement.

Teacher Enn's rewarding elements in Educating LSEnDs.

The experience of teacher Enn promotes the outcome of the directive of the department. Through this program, students with learning disabilities are provided with the necessary tools and support to succeed in their education, fostering a more inclusive and equitable learning environment for all. This belief manifests in her daily classroom practices, where vibrant visuals, colorful flashcards, and sensory-rich activities are carefully planned and implemented. Her meticulous preparation incorporating music, movement, and art into lessons demonstrates preparation and her commitment to engaging students through kinesthetic learning experiences.

..visualize a certain teaching philosophy as your direction of your professional growth. From this, strategize a career path and teaching methods. A belief that creativity was a key to unlock each LSEND potential. Everyday I always prepare colorful flashcards, some vibrant images and

simple words that captivate the different learners. Always have your checklist to understand each differences among your learners

..this kind of preparation shows your accomplishment and shows care of your student. Unprepared teachers inside the classroom show indirect character that is not interesting. These kinds of teachers always look into the challenging part of being a SNED teacher.

..reflecting on students' learning outcomes makes us complete our daily objective and our salaries are paid off properly.

Her teaching philosophy, rooted in the department's mission, emphasizes creativity to unlock the potential of diverse learners. Unlike those focused on SNED's challenges, she prioritizes proactive preparation, vibrant visuals, sensory activities, and individualized plans, demonstrating care and respect. Her reward moment isn't just academic achievement but the holistic development of her students. She associates in her equal value of enjoying a hard-earned meal, emphasizing the intrinsic rewards from the service when witnessing LSEND growth.

Teacher Enn's challenges in Educating LSEnDs.

Teacher Enn articulates numerous encounters faced in educating students with special needs (LSEND) in a country where the Special Needs Education (SNED) program is still developing. She highlights the pressing issues surrounding the implementation of effective interventions and the creation of supportive learning environments. The shortage of resources, particularly assistive technology for students with conditions like dyslexia, poses a significant barrier to achieving meaningful student development. Teacher Enn emphasizes that the lack of appropriate tools directly impacts teachers' abilities to provide quality education, illustrating the ongoing struggle to meet students' diverse needs. Through these challenges, teacher Enn acknowledges the positive steps being taken by the Department of Education, such as continuous professional development, the hiring of specialized teachers, and the provision of necessary resources. She hopes these efforts will lead to a more inclusive educational landscape, enabling teachers to better serve their students.

...in our country since SNED program is still very young, the pursuit of stability and improvement which shows so many challenges especially on the implementation of the proper interventive tool and environment for this kind of student. The shortage of resources and of a more inclusive learning environment. Like Dyslexia who struggle a lot if we don't have any assistive tool to enhance its readings skills. It take a lot of effort to achieved student development. Well, as of now the department of education already providing a continuous development from training, hiring of new specialize teachers, classroom and other resources needed.

..of the moment the lack of resources extends like assistive technology really considered in need of attention

..aside from the tool I consider is the number of teachers needed for the inclusive classroom are one to be considered which are also in need of attention for now. To create focus and give convenient consideration to their classroom preparation. Somehow all determined challenges, the department of education does not stop answering the necessary needs. In later times, we can eventually compete with the private sector.

Teacher Enn's work ethics centers on the development of SNED programs in a resource-constrained classroom, striving for more inclusive learning. The challenges of technology shortages and teacher scarcity highlight the Department of Education's proactive efforts in training, recruitment, and resource allocation. The perspective emphasizes bridging the gap between public and private education to ensure quality education for more families. This optimistic outlook focuses on future growth and positive impact, offering a hopeful vision for SNED's future despite current limitations.

Teacher Enn navigating through the challenges in educating LSENDs

In most cases, the activity established during classes, either departmental activity or school implementation program, creates class disruption and leads to delays and redirection of learning progress, especially in the LSEND. She highlights the significant challenges of educating students with special needs (LSEND) as stemming not only from the subject matter but primarily from unpredictable events and circumstances that can arise inside and outside the classroom. She emphasizes that various uncontrolled factors can influence classroom dynamics, so preparation in making classroom learning is crucial for teachers to be well-prepared.

..biggest challenge wasn't the subject matter, but the unpredictable events and dealings inside and outside school. Various activities and uncontrolled events. To get rid of these matters and avoid any of these circumstances that ends sacrificing the time engagement by the student is the daily preparation. It should start with your student evaluation from character and its individual differences. Align this output to your lesson objective assuring that it caters to the diverse environment in the classroom.

Teacher Enn emphasizes daily preparation and thorough student evaluations as crucial for effective teaching. The monitoring of student progress and individual differences should be tailored to lesson plans in order to meet diverse needs, anticipate potential learning barriers, and develop alternative strategies. Her flexible lesson plans accommodate various activities and circumstances, reflecting a commitment to engaging LSEND students beyond the traditional classroom setting. This proactive approach demonstrates her resilience and dedication to providing the best possible educational experience despite challenges.

Teacher Enn's Aspiration to the LSEND

The profound aspiration of teacher Enn for the future of special needs education. As patriotic, it emphasizes the critical role of passionate and dedicated teachers in achieving the Department's vision. Teacher Enn expresses a desire for the recruitment of new SNED teachers who not only possess the necessary skills and competencies but also share a deep love for their country and a commitment to empowering students with diverse needs. This aspiration extends beyond personal gain; it highlights a collective goal to contribute meaningfully to nation-building through education.

..the aspiration I have is that the vision of the department shall be achieved through hiring of new SPED teachers who passionately love our country and whose values and competencies enable the student to realize their full potential and contribute meaningfully to building the nation. Who have the desire to heartily do the job and its profession, eager to learn and able to accept the challenging environment. This passion is seen in those teachers who stayed in the service. A genuine public servant who always looks for the contribution to our nation building.

..looking forward to the recruitment and retention of dedicated special education (SPED) teachers who share a strong commitment to serving their country and fostering the potential of their student

..the teacher's unwavering hope for the future of special education and the nation's youth sets them apart, showcasing a powerful blend of patriotism and commitment to the transformative power of education.

Teacher Enn's experience highlights the importance of adaptable, dedicated teachers and faithful public servants who foster LSEND's potential. While motivation includes salary or career advancement, true character lies in the commitment to the profession and students. This perspective emphasizes the need for passion, dedication, and community responsibility in special education. Enn's aspiration for SNED reflects a belief in education's transformative power and the importance of teacher placement. Screening and recruitment are aimed at several qualified teachers with genuine passion who are able to contribute to the improvement of LSEND. Her narrative showcases a powerful blend of patriotism and a desire for positive societal impact through education.

Teacher Fay: The Stalwart

Teacher Fay has been a highly skilled and committed SNED teacher for eleven years, assigned to secondary-level LSEND, including deaf students. Holding a Bachelor's degree in Secondary Education (Special Education) and currently pursuing a Master's degree in the field, she demonstrates a commitment to ongoing professional development. As a regular SNED Teacher 1 in a public secondary high school, she teaches the SNED curriculum and manages the LSEND program, significantly contributing to inclusive education. A married woman, she advocates for quality education for students with diverse learning needs.

Teacher Fay's journey into special education was unexpected, initially driven by family circumstances and a gradual discovery of her resilience. Initially hesitant, she

found fulfillment and purpose in her work, highlighting how unexpected paths can lead to a rewarding career. Her journey, including time outside of education before returning, showcases the transformational potential of overcoming obstacles and developing latent skills. Her unwavering focus, personal growth, and dedication to public service distinguish her as an exceptional educator.

Teacher Fay's Motivation in Pursuing the Career.

Teacher Fay lives her mother's experience as a teacher in the United States and her passion for helping students succeed. She is dedicated to making a positive impact in the lives of her students and believes in the power of education to change lives. Teacher Fay reveals a journey of motivation shaped by familial influence, personal courage, and a deepening commitment to special education. Initially hesitant about pursuing a career in teaching, particularly in the challenging environment of special education, she was influenced by her mother's experiences and stories. While her mother's accounts of being a teacher in the US highlighted the difficulties and required bravery, it also ignited a curiosity about how her mother managed to thrive in such circumstances.

..my mother's stories initially made me hesitant to pursue higher education, but she always said, "If you want me to pay for your college, then you have to go." I knew I'd rather go than be unemployed and receive no allowance. Along with her stories, I was also curious about how she survived those difficult situations. I figured it wasn't just about income, since she had other skills, and I wanted to ask her more in-depth questions
...still my commitment is not strong, looking into my personality and having the fear of the possibilities considering teaching in the public school
..along with my experience for 10 years already and keep on tracking why I am here give me strong courage that this is my path
..the great thing about being a special education teacher is that every day is a new day; it's like having new students every day because their behavior changes constantly. There's no predictable pattern, so it's challenging but also very fulfilling.

Teacher Fay's journey from doubts to career direction in special education was fueled by her mother's influence and her own resilience. Initially hesitant along the way, found strength in familial support and the intrinsic value of the profession. Her experience as a car agent and peer support strengthened her decision. Later in time, she discovered hidden courage, transforming her approach and finding fulfillment in the daily challenges. Her story demonstrates how external and internal motivations converge to create a dedicated educator.

Teacher Fay's rewarding elements in Educating LSENDs.

The story of teacher Fay highlights the rewarding elements of her journey as a special needs education teacher, particularly in overcoming communication barriers with her deaf students. She acknowledges her initial challenges, especially regarding her

American/Filipino Sign Language (ASL) proficiency. Rather than allowing the doubts to sink in, she demonstrates resilience by committing to learning and improving her skills. Using resources like YouTube for self-education reflects her determination to bridge the communication gap and effectively support her students.

..when I had a deaf student, I wasn't sure if my American Sign Language (ASL) was accurate, but YouTube was a lifesaver. This meant I had to review my sign language skills. There were moments of doubt, but as long as I accepted the challenge, I knew I could overcome this barrier. I spent countless hours learning sign language, going beyond the basics. Eventually, I overcame my fear and gained confidence. I revisited the skills I knew would help my student.]

..patiently learning and was thinking I'd done it

..encouraging myself everyday to face the thoughts to help this students. Seeing them independently do their stuff often brings me to the realization that I am one of their hopes.

Teacher Fay dedicated countless hours to mastering sign language, which built her confidence and demonstrated her commitment to supporting the development of learners with special educational needs and disabilities (LSEND). She transformed her initial fears into a sense of empowerment, recognizing the direct impact she had on her students' communication and engagement. The emotional fulfillment she gains from helping students achieve independence and self-expression far outweighs the early challenges she faces. This deep connection and shared progress strengthen her belief in the value of her role, showing that the challenges in special education bring meaningful rewards for both teachers and students.

Teacher Fay's challenges in Educating LSENDs.

Improving special education teachers' strategic delivery and pedagogy in SNED programs begins with the Individualized Education Program (IEP). According to Teacher Fay's experience, the IEP is a foundation aligned with individualized learning plans for students with learning and special educational needs tailored to their specific abilities and requirements. Teachers often find this to be a challenge, particularly when crafting the IEP, aligning individual needs, and planning the content in relation to the available classroom resources. Since developing an effective IEP is complex, there should be a focus on reinforcing practical activities within the classroom. This approach provides a more personalized and practical educational experience for students with learning disabilities.

..the challenge I consider is the setting of IEP, since few of us sit down to craft the IEP that has measurable goals tailored to multiple students with different learning needs. Aside from the fact that we don't have exact

training, templates were made, the majority of the teachers have a hard time making this plan.

.. the courage to tell the parents on three things that they also need to do at home

..the facility and other learning resources we have in school, the learning material that we need. Most of our learning tools are done on our own (DIY).

..the classroom size number of enrollment surges every year. So, sometimes like the typical classroom setting are the reality in SNED, congested

Teacher Fay's challenges as a teacher were evident in the inadequate training and resources for IEP development, emotional labor in engaging resistant parents, reliance on personal funds for materials, and managing increased enrollment and classroom dynamics. Despite these obstacles, their commitment to student well-being drives them to find innovative solutions and maintain effective teaching strategies, demonstrating unwavering dedication to education.

Teacher Fay navigating through the challenges in educating LSENDs

Teacher Fay's response to navigating the challenges in Educating LSENDs is experience from the character of understanding communication and utilizing evidence-based strategies can significantly enhance the learning experience for students with special educational needs. The experience for students with special educational needs is enhanced through various activities and strategies. By incorporating multiple teaching methods and fostering, teachers can effectively navigate the challenges of educating LSENDs.

.. the wisdom first of my parents, she is my direct influence

..seeking wisdom from people who have been in the service, seeking for thoughts that will help you establish your ground for resolution of any problem you encounter.

..reflection about don't try to do everything yourself; have the courage to ask your colleagues for help, both new and experienced ones

This underscores the importance of mentorship and collaboration in overcoming the challenges of teaching, especially in special education. Seeking diverse perspectives from parents' wisdom and experiences from colleagues that offer options to address the difficulties in educating LSEND. The advice to proactively seek help emphasizes collaboration as an essential tool for improved lesson planning, resource sharing, and reducing feelings of isolation, creating a more supportive learning environment.

Teacher Fay's Aspiration for the LSENDs

Teacher Fay's aspiration reflects a strong commitment to creating an inclusive and supportive educational environment, particularly for students with LSEND student. Her vision emphasizes implementing strategies that guide and direct quality education. She

believes grouping students according to their abilities is essential for allowing all learners to engage meaningfully with the curriculum. By advocating for a smooth transition between lesson activities, Teacher Fay acknowledges the need for flexible teaching methods that accommodate diverse learning styles and paces, ultimately enhancing the overall dynamics of the classroom.

..my aspiration is to create a supportive, inclusive environment where students will be grouped according to their ability and have a smooth transition of the lesson activity and foster a sense of collaboration. This will promote a positive and engaging classroom atmosphere for an easy transition of learning in a more conducive to academic growth.

Teacher Fay aspires to create an engaging, inclusive classroom where students are motivated, minimizing supervision and maximizing focus on prepared activities. She envisions manageable class sizes and thoughtful grouping based on learning capabilities, reflecting a commitment to high-quality education. Her optimistic, proactive approach suggests a belief in the potential for change, showcasing her dedication to creating an environment where every child can thrive and highlighting the transformative power of education.

DISCUSSION

Teachers' Motivation to Pursuing a Career in SNED

This study examines the diverse motivations behind the career choices and sustained commitments of experienced special needs education (SNED) teachers with over 10 years of experience. Utilizing open-ended questions, it explores personal, professional, and social factors that influence their decisions. Investigating their initial motivations for entering the field, such as personal experiences, family support, and a desire to help others. The sub-themes that emerged from the study are nurturing the passion for LSEND, resonating with the family of LSEND, giving into family influence, having a desire to provide for family needs, and capitalizing on career opportunities.

Nurturing the Passion for LSENDs

Teachers Baze, Dayl, Enn, and Fay exemplify how personal backgrounds and familial experiences shape their commitment to special needs education, nurturing a passion for LSENDs. Their stories reflect a holistic approach that intertwines personal fulfillment with professional growth, its essence of being resilient, compassionate, and dedicated. This commitment transforms their lives and positively impacts the well-being of their LSEND students and their families. According to Darling-Hammond et al. (2020), passionate teachers are driven by deep motivation, fostering student development through innovative methods and collaboration. Nurturing this passion involves creating inclusive classrooms that celebrate diversity, employing evidence-based practices, and building strong partnerships with families and support services.

Resonating with the family of LSEND

The experiences of Teachers Abby, Baze, Cath, Dayl, Enn, and Fay highlight the profound impact of resonating with family life on their dedication to educating LSEND students. Each teacher's journey, whether raising a child with special needs, caring for a sibling with social challenges, or managing a large family, has fostered empathy and commitment to supporting LSEND students and their families. Their challenges enhance their understanding of the unique needs of these students (Comighud et al., 2022), fueling compassionate teaching practices and a drive for inclusive learning environments. This narrative emphasizes that personal connections empower educators and inspire hope for their students and families, underscoring the importance of shared understanding in achieving quality educational outcomes. Additionally, adequate salaries and incentives fuel teachers' need to meet their families' financial needs, promoting positive engagement and well-being. Supportive family environments can significantly enhance teachers' motivation and empathy, creating more effective and inclusive classrooms.

Giving into Family Influence

The experiences of Teachers Cathy and Fay illustrate the significant impact of familial influence on their commitment to special education, particularly as they come from families of teachers. Inheriting a teaching legacy involves more than imitation; it requires internalizing the values, challenges, and rewards of the profession. Witnessing their parents' dedication instilled in them a profound understanding of the complexities of teaching and its transformative potential, shaping their expectations and preparing them for the demands of their careers. This shared understanding fosters empathy and resilience, equipping them to navigate challenges and advocate effectively for their students. Their familial influence goes beyond inspiration, providing a framework for understanding the profession's intrinsic rewards and the profound impact educators can have on children with special needs.

Research indicates that family responsibility is essential for personal growth and social acceptance in special needs education, while family dynamics significantly shape career paths and motivations, influencing professional choices (Pabatang & Naparan, 2023).

Having a desire to provide for Family Needs

Teachers Baze and Cath exemplify the often-overlooked personal sacrifices teachers made to maintain balanced career aspirations with family responsibilities. Teacher Baze has a strong sense of duty to support their family financially, which can limit the time and energy available for professional development. Similarly, Teacher Cath's obligations to a large family may hinder her full commitment to her career, reducing job satisfaction and increasing stress. Relatively, Allam and Martin (2021) indicate that many teachers, particularly those with learning disabilities, lack specialized training, leaving them feeling unqualified to meet their students' needs.

Moreover, financial constraints, along with limited resources and insufficient training, further complicate their ability to create effective learning environments. Nonetheless, Zutiasari et al. (2021) state that the desire to support their families is a strong motivator for teachers, suggesting that addressing these barriers could enhance their participation and success in educational programs.

Capitalizing on Career Opportunities

Teacher Fay exemplifies the proactive pursuit of career paths in special education, driven by personal experiences that align with the challenges faced by students and their families. Teachers with similar backgrounds often develop similar deeper understanding of these needs, leading to more empathetic and effective teaching practices and benefit students in special education programs. Diverse backgrounds among teachers contribute to a more inclusive and supportive learning environment. According to Jingxiao et al. (2022) highlight the engaging activities driven by passion and fosters internal motivation to enhances work performance.

Thus, the narratives of teachers underscore the importance of nurturing resilience and adaptability, as these traits can enhance teaching effectiveness and career motivation, particularly in the context of family influence. This aligns with the Kaizen framework's emphasis on continuous improvement, which reflects the motivations of special education teachers dedicated to incremental enhancements driven by personal experiences, commitment to student growth, and advocacy for systemic change. By fostering resilience and adaptability, educators can better navigate challenges and persist in their efforts to create meaningful improvements in the lives of their students.

Teachers' Rewarding Aspect of Educating LSENDs students

This theme explores the teaching strategies employed by experienced Special Needs Education (SNED) teachers. Analysis reveals a prevalent use of personalized learning plans tailored to the individual needs of LSEND. Effective strategies frequently include visual aids and hands-on activities, demonstrably improving comprehension and retention. The rewarding aspect of being an SNED teacher is significantly derived from observing student breakthroughs, such as mastering challenging skills or gaining self-confidence. Furthermore, the unique perspectives and creativity of LSEND students provide unexpected rewards, underscoring the importance of adaptability and patience in a reciprocal learning environment. These themes will further examine the key sub-themes from this analysis: emotional support, continuous innovation in teaching strategies, expanded collaboration, and adaptability and resilience.

Emotional support

The narratives of Teacher Abby, Teacher Baze, and Teacher Cath highlight the rewarding aspect of emotional support in educating students with Learning, Social, Emotional, and Neurological Differences (LSEND). Teacher Abby emphasizes the fulfillment derived from observing her students' growth, while Teacher Baze finds joy in

the trust and connections fostered when students affectionately call her by name. Teacher Cath utilizes her childhood experiences to create engaging lessons that advocate for her students' needs. These teachers illustrate that building strong emotional connections is crucial for creating a supportive learning environment, enhancing academic performance, and promoting a positive school culture. This indicates that motivated SNED teacher, equipped with patience and empathy, play an important role in overcoming learning barriers and enhance positive student attitudes. Supporting the well-being and motivation of special education teachers is essential, as their emotional investments lead to increased student engagement and success, ultimately reinforcing their dedication to nurturing each student's growth (Jingxiao et al., 2022).

Continuous Innovative Teaching Strategies

The experiences of Teachers Dayl and Teacher Enn highlight the crucial role of ongoing innovation in effective special education pedagogy. Teacher Dayl focuses on creating an inclusive environment that addresses her students' unique challenges, emphasizing parental involvement and collaboration to enhance student development. Meanwhile, Teacher Enn utilizes vibrant visuals and sensory-based activities to engage her students, demonstrating that creativity is key to unlocking their potential through individualized learning plans. This points out that adaptability and diverse teaching methods allows educators to not only meet curriculum requirements but also inspire students to reach their full potential in ways that traditional methods may not. Research indicates that these innovative practices promote equity and inclusivity, enhancing teachers' self-efficacy and fulfillment while fostering meaningful relationships with students. Additionally, Jingxiao et al., (2022) effective teaching for students with special educational needs requires evidence-based instructional methods to create supportive classrooms that nurture individual talents and bridge achievement gaps.

Wider Scope of Collaboration

The narratives of Teachers Baze, Dayl, and Enn underlined the crucial role of collaboration in supporting LSEND students. Teacher Baze points out a family involvement while Teacher Dayl promotes open communication with parents, and Teacher Enn believes in the transformative power of teacher-family partnerships. This element of collaborative approach creates a strong support network that benefits students' academic and social well-being, similar to the Kaizen philosophy of continuous improvement through teamwork. By working together, teachers, families, and communities can create personalized interventions that address individual student needs, fostering holistic growth. However, achieving effective collaboration requires proactive efforts, as illustrated by the limited knowledge exchange between instrumental teachers and classroom teachers in the Wider Opportunities instrumental program (Johnson, 2024). This underscores the need for improved communication and knowledge sharing to maximize the benefits of collaborative support for LSEND students.

Adaptability and Resilience

Teachers Day and Teacher Enn's narratives showed characters of adaptability and resilience in special education. Teacher Dayl's commitment to individualized education plans (IEPs) and diverse learning styles and Teacher Enn's optimistic approach to resource gaps highlight the importance of these qualities for supporting LSEND students. Adaptability and resilience garner LSEND students' growth mindset, enabling teachers to continuously evolve their strategies while maintaining a positive outlook and overcoming classroom obstacles. This approach showed benefits to students that create a supportive learning environment. Ramos et al. (2023) state that the need for creative teaching tailored to individual student needs while fostering collaboration can lead to burnout; however, navigating these challenges builds valuable adaptability and resilience, ultimately rewarding teachers professionally.

Thus, the experiences of (SNED) teachers reveal that profound fulfillment in their work stems from emotional connections, innovative teaching strategies, and collaborative partnerships. Teachers find great joy in seeing their students succeed and building strong, supportive relationships. Their commitment to continuous improvement, akin to the Kaizen philosophy, is reflected in their pursuit of creative, adaptable teaching methods and proactive collaboration with families and the community. These findings underscore the importance of integrating empathetic understanding and innovative, individualized approaches in teacher training programs, particularly within the MAED SPED curriculum. These described fostering strong support networks and equipping future educators with the necessary skills; these programs can enhance the educational experiences and holistic development of LSEND students, ultimately leading to improved outcomes in and out of the classroom.

Teacher's Challenges face when educating the LSEND students

The narrative on the challenges and difficulties encountered by SNED teachers when educating LSEND learners showed discussion on classroom-based challenges arising from the unique needs of students with learning disabilities and will analyze the various barriers impeding adequate support. These barriers encompass resource limitations, training inadequacies, and attitudinal factors. The key sub-themes emerging from this analysis are mental and physical teacher fatigue, as well as the complexities inherent in the design of the individualized education program (IEP).

Mental-physical fatigue

Teacher Abby illustrates how to manage self-harming behaviors, Teacher Baze highlights the resource limitations hindering effective support, and Teacher Cath describes the overwhelming balance between instruction and addressing students' immediate emotional and behavioral needs. This affective-somatic strain that interplays between emotional and physical demands is a significant factor impacting teacher well-being and influencing the educational experience of LSEND students. The teaching profession inherently demands significant resilience, and stressors such as classroom

challenges, heavy workloads, and lack of support contribute to mental and physical fatigue. However, work-related self-efficacy can buffer against this stress, with higher self-efficacy correlating to lower levels of fatigue and burnout (Piceci et al., 2020). Addressing these challenges requires adequate school support and resources to foster a positive learning environment for all.

Complexities of IEP Design

Teachers Enn and Fay exemplify a proactive approach to addressing the complexities of IEP design, which addresses the challenges occurring in special education. Teacher Enn thus highlights the importance of bridging resource and training gaps, while Teacher Fay emphasizes creating effective individualized plans. Despite challenges such as inadequate training, limited resources, and difficulties in obtaining information from administrators or families, these teachers demonstrate resilience and adaptability, fostering a collaborative environment focused on positive change.

Significant challenges in IEP design and implementation, including insufficient training, administrative demands, and emotional strain, impact SPED teachers' well-being (Mangongon, 2023). However, their optimistic outlook and commitment to improvement underscore the potential for positive change through collaboration and dedicated efforts to support each student's unique needs.

Six special needs teachers' narratives illustrate a Kaizen-inspired commitment by continuous improvement in educating LSEND. Facing challenges like self-harm, resource limitations, and IEP development, these teachers demonstrate collaboration, adaptability, and resilience. Their dedication to strong student relationships and refined teaching strategies underscores the potential for positive change. Thus, the MAED SPED program should incorporate the following to prepare educators for inclusive classrooms related context to trauma-informed practices; training in emotional intelligence; resource management and advocacy skills; differentiated instruction methodologies; and strategies for effective collaboration with parents and other professionals.

Teachers Navigates the Challenges involved in Educating LSEND

Navigating the challenges of educating students with special educational needs (LSEND) requires teachers to draw on their experiences to effectively manage the difficulties they encounter, including emotional and physical strain as well as the complexities of Individualized Education Program (IEP) design.

The study revealed several key sub-themes from the participants' responses: Practicing Self-Care, Mustering the Courage to Ask for Help, Establishing Stronger Partnerships with Stakeholders, and Implementing Practical Interventions.

Navigating the Mental-physical fatigue through Practicing Self-care

Teachers need to incorporate self-care strategies and acknowledge the crucial role of self-care in navigating the mental and physical fatigue inherent in their profession. Through Teachers Abby, Baze, Cath, Dayl, Enn, and Fay demonstrated varied self-care practices from exercise and meditation to family time and collaborative support. Their narratives underscore the need for more structured program support to improve their profession. It is understood that self-care is essential for teacher well-being and fostering empathy and practical support for students (Dumilig & Abdulrahman, 2024). Teacher Cath's consideration of commitment to professional development further illustrates the relationship between self-improvement and empathetic relationships. Addressing teacher fatigue requires a multifaceted approach encompassing individual self-care practices, such as mindfulness, exercise, supportive communities (peer networks), and institutional policies promoting mental health and well-being (Gugulethu, 2022). This combined approach is essential for maintaining teacher health and resilience in teaching LSEND.

Navigating the Mental-physical fatigue through Mustering the courage to ask for help

The importance of having the courage to seek help and support is evident in the theme narrated by the experience of SNED teachers, which reveals a complex relationship with asking for assistance, often tied to their self-perceived strength and resilience. For instance, Teachers Abby and Baze openly acknowledge the significance of seeking support from colleagues and family to manage stress and prevent burnout. Other teachers, like Cath and Dayl, demonstrate more indirect ways of seeking help, such as reflecting on past successes and emphasizing collaboration. Teacher Enn focuses on maintaining a positive environment as a strategy for self-preservation, while Teacher Fay highlights the value of mentorship from parents and experienced colleagues. This reliance on shared knowledge and support systems showcases the benefits of creating a network that fosters growth and success in the classroom. By reaching out for help, teachers can enhance their well-being and effectiveness in educating their students.

Navigating the complexities of IEP design through Establishing a Stronger Partnership with Stakeholders

Teachers Baze, Cath, and Dayl's narrative provides the crucial role of stakeholder partnerships in navigating the complexities of IEP design for LSEND students. Teacher Baze illustrates the evolving role of the teacher in this profession, fostering collaboration, while Teacher Cath demonstrates how shared goals lead to success. Teacher Dayl's focus on building strong parent-teacher relationships underscores the importance of community engagement. Practical support for LSEND students requires a unified approach involving teachers, parents, and other stakeholders, fostering mutual trust and shared decision-making. According to Renfrow & Smith (2024) the increased stakeholder awareness, including the community, is essential for achieving the vision of more inclusive education, promoting acceptance, and enhancing community support. This collaborative approach improves educational outcomes and alleviates teacher isolation, transforming challenges into shared journeys toward success.

Navigating the complexities of IEP design through Implementing practical intervention

Teachers' proactive approaches in supporting LSEND students discover themes, creating a pedagogy for more practical intervention, characterized by flexibility and adaptability, highlight the power of preventative measures in creating effective learning environments. This proactive strategy, emphasizing anticipation and personalized interventions, contrasts with reactive crisis management, reducing the burden often associated with the challenges of this SNED profession. Implementing practical interventions in IEP development is crucial for alleviating teacher challenges, and this proactive approach aligns with the Kaizen philosophy of continuous improvement (Dumilig & Abdulrahman, 2024). By systematically evaluating and refining interventions, teachers can continuously improve IEP design and implementation, ultimately fostering student growth and self-determination.

Navigating the challenges of educating LSEND students through the lens of the Kaizen philosophy emphasizes the approach of teachers who reflect systematically on their strategies, seek feedback, and implement minor adjustments that enhance both teacher well-being and student outcomes. Focus thoroughly on fostering a culture of self-management and collaboration, particularly involving all responsible parties in the IEP process, teachers can create culturally responsive interventions tailored to student needs. This proactive mindset helps identify and address underlying issues and promotes resilience within the educational environment. Adopting the Kaizen philosophy ultimately leads to improved teaching strategies and more effective support for students with special educational needs (Urbani et al., 2024).

Teachers Aspiration to LSEND students

Teachers working with LSEND students aspire to create a more effective and equitable educational system. Their key goals include standardized, high-quality programs; curricula fostering independent learning and life skills; and the development of highly skilled, adaptable teachers. This desire is reflected in sub-themes emphasizing more authentic, inclusive practices, stronger advocacy for independent learning, and the need for more trained and proficient special needs educators.

More Authentic Inclusive Practices for LSENDs Education

The narrative of Teachers Abby and Fay exemplifies authentic character through inclusive practices for LSEND students. Teacher Abby's personal connection to special education drives her to view challenges as opportunities for empowerment, focusing on nurturing individual strengths and fostering independence. Teacher Fay creates a supportive classroom environment through thoughtful grouping and engaging activities, promoting collaboration and a sense of belonging. These narratives highlight that authentic inclusivity goes beyond mere access to education; it involves actively aligning educational practices with individual student needs and fostering a sense of belonging. This approach recognizes and nurtures individual strengths and is essential for achieving positive academic outcomes for students with disabilities (Nuñez & Tantiado, 2025).

Successful inclusive education requires addressing challenges such as inadequate infrastructure and teacher training, and promoting societal acceptance of disability as part of diversity.

Stronger Advocacy of Independent Learning for LSENDs

Teachers Abby, Baze, and Cath showed a strong advocacy for independent learning in SNED, a commitment to empowering students with disabilities to become self-sufficient. Teacher Abby's personal experience sparks her passion for fostering independence and functional life skills, enabling students to thrive in their communities. Teacher Baze and Teacher Cath have similar priorities in individualized education plans and real-world applications to promote autonomy and self-reliance. Their emphasis on Dumilig & Abdulrahman (2024) verifies that the functional skills and emotional growth underscore a belief in the transformative power of education to nurture independence and equip students to confidently participate in society. This advocacy highlights the importance of equipping teachers with effective strategies, including differentiated instruction, assistive technologies, and clear goal-setting, to support students in taking charge of their own learning journeys.

Placement of More Trained and Proficient SNED Teacher

Proficiency in SPED involves a deep understanding of diverse learning needs and the ability to adapt teaching methods, which is evident in Teachers Abby and Baze, who have improved teacher proficiency, emphasizing the need for training in adapting strategies, creating inclusive environments, and fostering collaboration to meet diverse learning needs. This aspiration, shared by several teachers, underscores the need for standardized, high-quality programs and a commitment to promoting independent learning. However, significant challenges exist, including recruitment and retention difficulties, inadequate training in evidence-based practices, and resource constraints. Addressing these challenges through comprehensive teacher training and professional development, informed by the Kaizen philosophy of continuous improvement, is crucial for providing high-quality, inclusive education that empowers students with disabilities (Dumilig & Abdulrahman, 2024).

The aspirations of SNED teachers point towards a transformative shift in special education, emphasizing a holistic approach and connecting systemic improvements with individual teacher growth. Meaningful change requires empowering teachers with the necessary training, tools, and support to meet diverse learning needs and foster inclusivity and independence in LSEND students (Florian & Camedda, 2017). This vision necessitates investment in professional development, inclusive infrastructure, and curriculum flexibility to ensure teachers and students thrive.

Conclusions

Based on the study's findings, the study concluded that female SNED (Special Needs Education) teachers, who are married and have ten or more years of experience

in special needs education, often have a strong personal connection to individuals with disabilities through their families. Their motivation is driven by a commitment to supporting learners with special educational needs and disabilities (LSEs), influenced by their family experiences, the desire to address family needs, and the pursuit of career opportunities.

The rewarding aspects of their work include providing emotional support, using innovative teaching strategies, fostering collaboration, and demonstrating adaptability and resilience. However, these teachers also face challenges, such as mental and physical fatigue, along with the complexities involved in designing Individualized Education Programs (IEPs). To cope with mental and physical fatigue, teachers prioritize self-care and actively seek help when needed. They address the complexities of IEPs by building stronger partnerships with stakeholders and implementing effective interventions.

Ultimately, the aspirations of SNED teachers for LSEs focus on promoting authentic inclusive practices, advocating for independent learning, and increasing the number of trained and proficient SNED teachers.

Teachers' experiences demonstrate Kaizen's characterization from the iterative problem-solving, teachers' reflection, teachers' collaboration, and emotional connection that create more effective and inclusive learning environments, improving teacher well-being and transforming special education into a learner-centered, equitable system.

Recommendations

In light of the current research gap, where most studies on Special Education focus primarily on teaching strategies and inclusive education policies, this study recommends a more comprehensive and inclusive approach to SNED research and program development. A program that addresses the personal motivations, emotional struggles, and professional challenges SNED teachers face, particularly those working with LSEs. The stakeholders, such as parents, educators, DepEd officials, corporate partners, academic institutions, and community members, should collaborate to provide holistic support systems, address the teacher's well-being, enhance differentiated instruction and IEP training, and promote inclusive values. Future research should also include the perspectives of LSE students and their families, ensuring that real-life experiences inform policies and programs of those at the heart of special needs education.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study strictly followed ethical guidelines throughout its entirety. Informed consent was obtained from all participants after they were thoroughly informed about the study's purpose, procedures, and confidentiality measures. Participants were assured that they had the right to withdraw at any time without facing any consequences, and their privacy and anonymity were fully protected. All personal and sensitive information was

kept strictly confidential and stored securely. The research was conducted impartially, free from any conflicts of interest, and all sources were properly acknowledged to prevent plagiarism. The data collected were used solely for academic purposes, and the well-being of all participants was prioritized at every stage of the study.

Acknowledgments

The researcher expresses heartfelt gratitude to the Almighty Father for His constant guidance and grace throughout this academic journey. Sincere thanks are extended to the Graduate School Professors of Saint Columban College of Pagadian, especially to Dr. Janus G. Naparan, for his invaluable mentorship and support as thesis adviser. The researcher is deeply thankful to his family, for their love, inspiration, and unwavering support. This study would not have been possible without their collective encouragement and support.

REFERENCES

- Allam, F. C., & Martin, M. M. (2021). Issues and challenges in special education: A qualitative analysis from a teacher's perspective. *Southeast Asia Early Childhood Journal*, 10(1), 37–49. <https://doi.org/10.37134/saecj.vol10.1.4.2021>
- Camedda, D., & Florian, L. (2017). Effective inclusive teacher education for special educational needs and disabilities: Some more thoughts on the way forward. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 61, 164–178. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2016.09.007>
- Comighud, S. M. T., & Arevalo, M. J. (2021). Motivation in relation to teachers' performance. In UBT International Conference (p. 507). UBT University. <https://knowledgecenter.ubt-uni.net/conference/2021UBTIC/all-events/507>
- Darling-Hammond, L., Flook, L., Cook-Harvey, C., Barron, B., & Osher, D. (2020). Implications for educational practice of the science of learning and development. *Applied Developmental Science*, 24(2), 97-140.
- DepEd Order no. 53 s. 2008 Maximization of Trained Teachers and Administrators in Special Education
- DepEd Order No. 38 s. 2015 Guideline on the Utilization of Support Funds for Special Education Program
- DepEd order no. 44 s. 2021 Policy Guidelines on the Provision of Educational program and Services for Learner with Disabilities in K12 Education Program
- Dumilig, R., & Abdulrahman, A. (2024). Belief in the Young: Journey of SPED Receiving Teachers in Teaching Learners with Special Education Needs. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 16(8), 839-844. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10559472>

- Dumilig, R. J. P., & Abdulrahman, A. G. (2024). Empowering learners with special educational needs: Strategies for fostering independence. *Psychology and Education*, 16(8), 839–844. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10559472>
- Florian, L., & Camedda, D. (2017). Effective inclusive teacher education for special educational needs and disabilities: Some more thoughts on the way forward. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 61, 164–178. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2016.09.007>
- García-Martínez, I., Rodríguez-Fuentes, M. J., & García-Sánchez, J. N. (2022). Assessment of public special education teachers' training needs on evidence-based practice for students with autism spectrum disorders in Spain. *Children*, 9(1), 83. <https://doi.org/10.3390/children9010083>
- Gugulethu, J. (2022). Impact of a mindfulness-based intervention on stress and burnout among physical education teachers in South Africa. *International Journal of Physical Education, Recreation and Sports*, 9(2), 45–58. <https://doi.org/10.47604/ijpers.2279>
- Jingxiao, Z., Gangzhu, G., Lin, X., Inayat, K., Weidong, L., & Simon, P. (2022). The moderating effect of learning experience on learning motivation and learning outcomes of international students. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.913982>
- Johnson, A. (2024). Equipping educators for learning support: A systematic review. *British Journal of Special Education*, 51(1), 45–60. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-8578.12522>
- Mangongon, F. A. A. (2023). Challenges encountered by special educators: Inputs for the improvement of the individualized education program. *AIDE Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 2(1), 136–150. <https://doi.org/10.56648/aide-irj.v2i1.25>
- Núñez, A. A., & Tantiado, R. C. (2025). Teachers' well-being and attitude towards the inclusion of special needs education (SNED) learners. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Analysis*, 8(2), Article 34. <https://doi.org/10.47191/ijmra/v8-i02-34>
- Pabatang, L. C. I., & Naparan, J. A. (2024). Lived experiences of a Tagasalo having siblings with special needs: An educational implication. *Journal of Educational Management and Instruction (JEMIN)*, 3(2), 135–148. <https://doi.org/10.22515/jemin.v3i2.8618>
- Piceci, L., Sgorlon, A., & Peluso Cassese, F. (2020). Stress of teachers: The transition to distance learning during the COVID-19. *QTimes – Journal of Education, Technology and Social Studies*, 12(3), 356–368. <https://doi.org/10.32068/QT12-3-2020-27>
- Polkinghorne, D. E. (1995). Narrative configuration in qualitative analysis. *International Journal of Qualitative Studies in Education*, 8(1), 5–23. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0951839950080103>
- Ramos, L. R., Sánchez, S., Scyner, G., & Amigón, R. (2023). Teacher adaptability to change in special education: Creativity and commitment to the institution. *Canadian Journal of Educational and Social Studies*, 3(2), 86–96. <https://doi.org/10.53103/cjess.v3i2.131>

- Renfrow, J., & Smith, H. M. (2024). Stronger IEP teams. *Principal Leadership*, 25(4). <https://www.nassp.org/publication/principal-leadership/volume-25-2024-2025/principal-leadership-december-2024/stronger-iep-teams/>
- Urbani, J. M., LePage, P., & Watson-Alvarado, S. (2024). Building and sustaining a collaborative educational team: Teachers and paraprofessionals. *TEACHING Exceptional Children*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00400599241231215>
- Zutiasari, I., Rahayu, W. P., Martha, J. A., & Zumroh, S. (2021). Barriers to entrepreneurship education for disabilities in Indonesia. Atlantis Press. <https://www.atlantispress.com/proceedings/bistic-21/125963896>